

Can a Hellenic Air-Force Pilot Become an Astronaut?

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Abstract

One of the most emblematic dimensions of outer space is the astronauts, who symbolize human exploration and the quest for knowledge. Since its inception, U.S. NASA has selected 360 astronaut candidates: 212 military and 138 civilians; 191 pilots and 169 non-pilots. The majority of astronauts remain in the military, a trend likely to continue due to the unique skills and abilities pilots bring to space missions. This article briefly describes the selection criteria for the first astronauts internationally, highlighting the significant role of pilots. It also explores the past initiative of the Hellenic Ministry of Defence to select a Greek astronaut from the Air Force, aligning with international practices and providing direction for future efforts.

Keywords:

Hellenic Air Force; Pilots; Astronauts; Space Exploration; Military Personnel; Hellenic Ministry of Defence.

1. The Recognition of the Dimension of Space in the Hellenic Air Force Doctrine

The realm of space plays a pivotal role in the sphere of modern military operations. Satellite systems orbiting Earth provide critical operational capabilities such as global communication, earth observation, navigation, and early warning. These capabilities allow the Armed Forces to maintain uninterrupted connectivity and monitor the movements of adversaries, effectively assisting in the planning and execution of military operations.

At the same time, it is worth noting the significance of their contribution to disaster prediction and response, humanitarian assistance guidance and intelligence gathering. This enables military forces to operate and respond effectively to a broad range of security challenges. Consequently, the operational exploitation of space enhances situational awareness, operational planning, and the overall effectiveness of defence strategies, reaffirming the crucial role of space in global security and defence.

In the context of modern Greek reality, the recognition of space as a dimension is evident in the military doctrine of the Hellenic Air Force. With the recent revision of the doctrine (March 2023), space has been officially acknowledged for the first time by an institutional document of the Hellenic Armed Forces as a vital domain for safeguarding and advancing national interests. The concept of "Space Power" has been recognized and placed prominently in the Armed Forces, fundamentally upgrading all three levels of warfare (strategic, tactical, and operational), thus serving as an undeniable force multiplier in modern battlefields.

*Revolutionizing Connectivity through Satellite Technology*¹

Furthermore, the emergence of the Space dimension by the Hellenic Air Force can ensure the potential for further development, evolution, and qualitative improvement in the planning and execution of multi-domain operations in today's multidimensional battlefield.² A similar initiative was undertaken on December 20, 2019, by the President of the United States of America Donald J. Trump, who institutionalized the Space Force as a separate branch of the U.S. Armed Forces. This move reflects the evolution of strategic thinking regarding Space and highlights its value in safeguarding national interests and maintaining national security and defence.³

However, the symbolic dimension of space presents an equally important and intriguing aspect beyond its operational utilization, the spaceflight. This term refers to astronautics and is conducted by individuals with specific qualifications who actively contribute to human exploration and the advancement of scientific knowledge.

Astronauts are educated and professionally distinguished individuals who have left their mark in the annals of world history, inspiring and motivating humanity along the path of exploration. This is admirable and praiseworthy. Nevertheless, it may prompt reflection as to why Greece, as a country, has not yet seen a Greek citizen - military or civilian - join the elite ranks of astronauts and serve as a role model for Greek society.

2. The First Astronauts

The origins of astronautics can be historically traced back to the Cold War era (1945-1991) between the United States of America (USA) and the Soviet Union (USSR). During this period, the two nations engaged in an endless competition for dominance in Space (Space Race), which fundamentally altered levels of human knowledge and exploration. The first major milestone focused on placing the first human in space. This was achieved by the Soviet Union on April 12, 1961, when cosmonaut Yuri Gagarin left Earth's atmosphere for 108 minutes aboard the Vostok 1 capsule. This mission was considered a tremendous success by the standards of the time, as it marked the first instance of a human leaving Earth's atmosphere, making Gagarin an international hero within Soviet society. ⁴

Alan B. Shepard, May 5, 1971 ⁶

The American response came just three weeks later when astronaut Alan B. Shepard became the first American citizen to conduct a suborbital flight aboard the Mercury Freedom 7 capsule. However, the significant decision and the ultimate goal of the space race were articulated three weeks later, when U.S. President John F. Kennedy declared in a speech the ultimate objective of the U.S. space program: landing the first human on the Moon before the end of the 1970s. ⁵

In 1959, for the first time in history, NASA in its search for astronauts, requested the U.S. Air Force to prepare a list of members meeting specific criteria. Attention was focused on individuals with flight experience and a background in engineering. The list was initially narrowed down to 500 individuals, and those who stood out and were

selected as the first astronauts were M. Scott Carpenter, L. Gordon Cooper, John H. Glenn, Virgil I. “Gus” Grissom, Walter M. Schirra, Alan B. Shepard, and Donald K. “Deke” Slayton, also known as the Mercury Seven.

From 1964 onwards, the criteria were revised, and NASA focused on individuals with strong academic backgrounds, such as master's or doctoral degrees in engineering, physical sciences, and medicine. These selected individuals formed the scientific community of astronauts, which was considered of primary importance in space exploration.⁷

*The Mercury 7 Astronauts: NASA's First Space Travelers*⁸

In 1978, the Space Shuttle was launched for the first time, crewed by five astronauts from NASA's 8th series, four of whom were pilots from the USAF and one a scientist (astronomer). Interest was now centered on the scientific exploration of space and the construction of an International Space Station capable of conducting scientific experiments aimed at further understanding the universe and Earth. This aspiration began to materialize in 1998 and was completed after ten years with the contribution of fifteen countries and a total of thirty space missions.

It is an undeniable fact that to this day that the preference for pilots has stood out, if not dominated, in the field of astronautics. This is mainly due to the skills that a pilot develops, such as enhanced space perception, three-axis movement, alertness, determination and the ability to multitask.

A special category of pilots, which has the greatest impact in the field of astronautics, is that of Test Pilots. The reason why test pilots stand out is their deep knowledge of flight and flying physiology, as they fly in aircraft of unknown performance and limits, a fact that cultivates instincts such as enhanced virtual-acoustic perception, alertness and decisiveness in decision-making and initiatives, in an environment where consequences truly count. The first space vehicles were constructions of unknown limits and capabilities.

For this reason, it was considered necessary that the first astronauts who would be called upon to operate them be former fighter aircraft test pilots, as only they could to a certain extent simulate the performance, speed and handling skills required of a space capsule.⁹

3. The Role of Military Personnel in Modern Astronauts

Modern astronaut missions, due to their complex nature and high demands, require adequate and appropriate crew training and preparation. This training focuses on technical expertise, survival in harsh conditions, physical fitness improvement, scientific education, and preparation for upcoming space exploration.

These requirements make the role of military personnel extremely important and multidimensional. Military training, particularly in the Air Force, which has a flight element, shares many commonalities with astronaut training, making this branch of the Armed Forces highly preferable.

Hellenic Airforce (H.A.F) Rafale H3-R Jets¹⁰

Military personnel, especially pilots, have valuable experience in managing dangerous and critical situations, coordinating crews, and adhering to mission schedules. These skills are vital for the effectiveness of space missions. History has shown that combining military expertise and astronautics shapes disciplined and fully prepared individuals capable of taking responsibility for space missions and meeting any risky demands.

An example worth noticing, is the Gemini VIII mission that took place on March 16, 1966, in which astronauts Neil Armstrong and David Scott attempted a space

rendezvous and docking of two different spacecraft. Minutes after the successful docking, the astronauts faced a series of malfunctions that caused the unified spacecraft to spin at a rate of one full rotation in less than a second.

This was masterfully handled by former test pilot and fighter aircraft pilot Neil Armstrong (and the first man to set foot on the Moon), as he managed to regain control manually, thus demonstrating the great importance of aviation training in addressing the unexpected of space.¹¹

*Neil Armstrong and David Scott after Gemini VIII Mission*¹²

The first selection of astronauts (Mercury Seven), focused exclusively on military personnel, as NASA was in close cooperation with the US Department of Defence at the time. In the following years, many believed that space exploration, especially by humans, should be a civilian, not a military, pursuit.

This view was strongly opposed by the US Air Force, which argued that space flight had many inherent characteristics with that on Earth and that Space was simply an extension of the scope of its operational scope. At the same time, an equally widespread view was that until then, human exploration and discovery of new areas had been carried out mainly by civilians, not by military forces. This fact led to the modification of the selection restrictions and opened the path of astronautics to many civilians.

Since its inception, NASA has selected 360 astronaut candidates: 212 military and 138 civilians; 191 pilots and 169 non-pilots. The absolute majority of astronauts remains

in the military, a percentage that is unlikely to decrease, considering that space exploration will always require the skill and abilities possessed by a pilot.¹³

The question that arises and may essentially concern the Hellenic Air Force is whether a Greek pilot could meet the difficulties and high demands of astronautics and why it has not already been done, given that a specific path for selecting astronauts is observed and at a time when more than 60% of the global astronaut community are former military personnel and pilots in particular.

Space Shuttle Launch April 4, 1983¹⁴

4. Hellenic Minister of Defence Guideline for a HAF Astronaut

In Greece, to date, there has been one astronaut of Greek descent, Theodore Yurchikhin, who participated in the 2002 joint American - Russian Atlantis mission and later (2006-2007) worked on the International Space Station (ISS).

The Greek government's willingness to select an astronaut was first expressed in 2003 by the Minister of Development, who conveyed the country's desire to explore the possibility of selecting and training an astronaut to the Director of External Relations of ESA (European Space Agency) and former Belgian Minister of Defence, Jean-Pol Poncelet. The Greek request at the time, concerned the individual national selection and training of a Greek astronaut, given that there was no open ESA astronaut selection competition in progress at that time.

Theodore Yurchikhin (bottom row, center) with the Expedition 37 and 38 crew ¹⁵

Two years later, the Minister of Defence, Spiros Spiliotopoulos, a former pilot of the Hellenic Air Force, showed genuine interest in the scenario of selecting an astronaut from the HAF personnel. To this end, he accepted a relevant proposal from the Space Office of the Ministry of Defence Staff, which was established in 2005 following a suggestion by the Hellenic Air Force. ESA, through its representative Daniel Sacotte, responded positively to the Greek request. An initial cost estimate for astronaut training was set at 20 million euros. ¹⁶

Interest was focused on the ranks of the Hellenic Air Force, as the required qualifications included completing over 1,000 hours in high-performance aircraft (fighter jets), a test pilot license, a master's or doctoral degree in the physical sciences, and fluency in Russian. However, none of the Hellenic Air Force personnel met all those qualifications. The change in ministerial leadership eventually diminished the enthusiasm for astronaut selection.

Although the Greek effort to select an astronaut has not garnered significant attention from subsequent governments, it has not deterred citizens of Greece from applying to ESA's open astronaut selection competitions. Two particularly inspiring examples are that of Aeronautical Engineer and ATPL pilot Dr. Panagiotis Vitsas, and former Fighter Pilot and holder of two Postgraduate Diplomas, Major (HAF, ret) Ioannis Lignos. Both managed to advance in ESA's 2021 astronaut selection reaching the fourth and third stage of the competition respectively. Given these data, it is hoped that in the future another Greek will manage to complete their effort, highlighting Greece and the Air Force, provided that the astronaut comes from its ranks.

5. Epilogue

Becoming an astronaut, from the early days of space exploration to the present, highlights the critical role of skilled pilots and military personnel in advancing human presence in space. Looking ahead, the role of astronauts will continue to evolve, driven by technological advancements and the expanding frontiers of space exploration. The Hellenic Ministry of Defence's initiative to select an astronaut from the Air Force exemplifies a forward-thinking approach, aligning with international practices and recognizing the strategic importance of space. By fostering such initiatives, Greece can contribute to the global effort of space exploration and inspire future generations to reach for the stars. The path to becoming an astronaut is demanding, but with dedication, expertise, and international collaboration, it remains an attainable goal for many aspiring space explorers.

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Short Biography:

Second Lieutenant (Pilot) Margos Georgios Marios graduated from the Hellenic Air Force Academy in 2024. He has accumulated a total of 150 flying hours in Technam P2002JF and T-6 Texan II aircrafts. Currently, he is undergoing advanced jet training on the M-346 Aermacchi Jet at the 120 IFTC (International Flight Training Center), further honing his skills in fast-jet operations and combat aviation. He is particularly interested in the expansion of the role of Air Power in Space. His HAFA thesis focused on "The Role of Mega-Constellations of small Satellites in Defence."